

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP5.6

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, BIOR, CVRL, IZSS, UNF, UH, IP, LRUJ, NPI, SDAS, COMSATS, VTL

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP22-WP5.6
Project Acronym	MEME
Author	Adriano Casulli
Other contributors	All participants
Due month of the report	49
Actual submission month	52
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	Save date: 10 June 2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

ANNUAL INTERIM ONLINE MEETING OF MEME

Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain

MEME annual meeting: 15 February 2022

AGENDA:

PART1: WPs (synthesis of what has been done till now)

- 8:45-9:00. *People connected to Teams*
- 9:00-9:10. **MEME project:** aims, overview, current achievements [Casulli, ISS]
- 9:10-9:20. **WP1 achievements: SAMPLING STRATEGY [T1-T3] (WP ended)** [Karamon, PIWET] *≤10 min*
- 9:20-9:30. **WP2 achievements: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS [T1-T3]** [Umhang and/or Boue, ANSES] *≤10 min*
- 9:30-9:40. **WP3 achievements: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS [T1-T9]** [Maksimov, FLI] *≤10 min*

PART2: Pending tasks (targets till the end of MEME)

- 9:40-9:50. **MEME roadmap:** pending activities [Casulli, ISS]
- **WP2 achievements: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS**
- 9:50-10:00. **T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay** [Davidson and/or Oines, NVI]
- 10:00-10:20. *Coffee break*
- **WP3: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS**
- 10:20-10:30. **T1. New molecular markers for Em and EgsI** [ST1: new mitochondrial markers; ST2: New microsatellite markers; ST3: NGS-based method]. [Saarma, UT] *10 min* [Umhang, ANSES] *10 min*
- 10:30-10:40. **T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE/NGS** [Davidson and/or Oines, NVI]

- 10:40-10:50. **T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques** [[Umhang, ANSES](#)]
- 10:50-11:00. **T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg** [[ST1: lettuces; new ST2: berries](#)] [[Umhang, ANSES](#)]
- 10:00-11:10. **T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas** [[Karamon, PIWET](#)]
- 11:10-11:20. **T8. Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE** [[new ST1, ST2, ST3](#)] [[Casulli, ISS](#)]

WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION & PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES

- 11:20-11:30. **T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3**
 - 1) Assessment of *newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques* [[To be discussed in WP3-T5](#)] [[Umhang, ANSES](#)]
 - 2) *Harmonization of Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assays* [[Davidson](#) and/or [Oines, NVI](#)] *5 min*
 - 3) *Harmonization of Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE and NGS* [[Jokelainen, SSI](#)] *5 min*
- 11:30-12:30. **Roundtable on WPs & Tasks**

PARTICIPANTS

Bastien, Fanny (**ANSES, France**) fanny.bastien@anses.fr
Berg, Rebecca (**SSI, Denmark**) rebe@ssi.dk
Bonelli, Piero (**IZSS, Italy**) piero.bonelli@izs-sardegna.it
Boue, Franck (**ANSES, France**) Franck.BOUÉ@anses.fr
Casulli, Adriano (**ISS, Italy**) adriano.casulli@iss.it
Conraths, Franz Josef (**FLI, Germany**) Franz.Conraths@fli.de
Davidson, Rebecca (**NVI, Norway**) Rebecca.Davidson@vetinst.no
Deksne, Gunita (**BIOR, Latvia**) Gunita.Deksne@bior.lv
Franssen Frits (**RIVM, The Netherlands**) frits.franssen@rivm.nl
João Gargaté, Maria (**INSA, Portugal**) m.joao.gargate@insa.min-saude.pt
Jokelainen, Pikka (**SSI, Denmark**) pijo@ssi.dk
Juurik, Triinu (**VFL, Estonia**) triinu.juurik@vetlab.ee
Karamon, Jacek (**PIWET, Poland**) j.karamon@piwet.pulawy.pl
Kärssin, Age (**VFL, Estonia**) Age.Karssin@vetlab.ee
Maas, Miriam (**RIVM, The Netherlands**) miriam.maas@rivm.nl
Maksimov, Pavlo (**FLI, Germany**) Pavlo.Maksimov@fli.de
Masala, Giovanna (**IZSS, Italy**) giovanna.masala@izs-sardegna.it
Moks, Epp (**VFL, Estonia**) Epp.Moks@vetlab.ee
Øines, Øivind (**NVI, Norway**) oivind.oines@vetinst.no
OShaughnessy, James (**DAFM, Ireland**) James.OShaughnessy@agriculture.gov.ie
Saarma, Urmas (**UT, Estonia**) urmas.saarma@ut.ee

Santolamazza, Federica (**ISS, Italy**) federica.santolamazza@iss.it

Santoro, Azzurra (**ISS, Italy**) azzurra.santoro@iss.it

Santucci, Cinzia (**IZSS, Italy**) cinzia.santucci@izs-sardegna.it

Samorek-Pierog, Malgorzata (**PIWET, Poland**) Malgorzata.Samorek-Pierog@piwet.pulawy.pl

Stensvold, Rune (**SSI, Denmark**) run@ssi.dk

Umhang, Gérald (**ANSES, France**) Gerald.UMHANG@anses.fr

van der Ark, Kees (**RIVM, The Netherlands**) kees.van.der.ark@rivm.nl

Waap, Helga (**INIAV, Portugal**) helga.waap@iniav.pt

Wassermann, Marion (**SU, Germany**) marion.wassermann@uni-hohenheim.de

Juurik, Triinu (**VFL, Estonia**) triinu.juurik@vetlab.ee